

An Empirical Study of NEP 2020 among Selected Students and Teachers in the State of Gujarat

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Abstract : *The National Education Policy 2020 aims to reform the existing education system from elementary to higher education vocational and teacher training in India, to provide industry-ready manpower and holistic development.*

Purpose :

The study was conducted to examine the awareness and perception among teachers and students from Gujarat to apprehend the opinion of two major stakeholders of the NEP 2020.

Methodology :

The study examines the level of awareness and perception among selected teachers and students from Gujarat with the help of a structured questionnaire from more than 500 respondents including 324 students and 204 teachers using a convenience purposive sampling method. The study is empirical in nature. The awareness and the perception of students and teachers of Gujarat are measured with 5 5-point Likert scale.

Outcome :

The research findings indicate a noteworthy distinction in the degree of NEP 2020 awareness between male and female teachers and students. Teachers who have worked for more than 15 years are more knowledgeable about and supportive of NEP 2020. Students pursuing postgraduate degrees and other advanced degrees are also more cognizant of and supportive of NEP 2020.

Keywords : National Education Policy, Awareness, Perception.

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Introduction

The National Education Policy, was approved on July 29, 2020, aims to reform India's education system, incorporating vocational training and industry-ready manpower, and fostering holistic development in both academic and non-academic spheres. (Panditrao & Panditrao, 2020) Looking back, India has implemented three education policy reforms: the first in 1968, the second in 1986 (updated in 1992), and the third in 2020. (Devi & Cheluvvaraju, 2020) The new education policy aims to develop logical thinkers, compassionate, resilient, and ethically minded individuals, fostering an egalitarian, inclusive, and plural society as per the Constitution. (Ministry of Human Resource Development, 2020)

The policy also aims to overhaul core programs, simplify board exams, and focus on experiential learning and critical thinking as per (Pawar et al., 2022) The NEP-2020 policy shifts from a 10+2 structure to a "5+3+3+4" approach, focusing on age groups 3-8 years, 8-11 years, 11-14 years, and 14-18 years, including babyhood education and pre-school education for children aged 3-5 under formal schooling. (Khan & Bhatnagar, 2019) (Pawar et al., 2022) But this aim cannot be fulfilled if the stakeholders of the policy are not aware of it or have a negative perception towards it.

The National Education Policy 2020 aims for comprehensive, quality education in natural or regional languages for students until category five. It recommends phasing out single-stream organizations and aiming for multidisciplinary universities and faculties by 2040. The policy addresses India's growing biological process needs and emphasizes the importance of learning skills alongside learning. (Pawar et al., 2022)(Ministry of Human Resource Development, 2020) Education reforms aim to ensure quality, integrity, and equity in learning outcomes from schooling to educational activity. Theoretical understanding is emphasized through pedagogies that focus on communication, discussion, debate, research, and cross-disciplinary thinking. Commerce and Management education needs continuous revision to develop students' creative potential and meet evolving industrial and social demands. Programs should be periodically revisited through stakeholder involvement to meet their expectations and meet education policy needs. (Akareem & Hossain, 2016)

The education in Commerce and Management should be outcome-based, with a selection-based system (CBCS) for undergraduate and postgraduate stages. Outcome-based education defines program objectives, program objectives, and course objectives, with student progression assessed based on achievement

status. Core subjects should combine theory and practical application, while open elective courses provide knowledge and skills across various areas, allowing for holistic education and specialization in practical areas. (Panditrao & Panditrao, 2020)

Review of Literature

(Choi, 2017) explores teachers' resistance to pedagogical changes in South Korea, focusing on the subtle, low-profile opposition to teaching English in English reform. Drawing on Foucault and Scott's writings, the study provides a comprehensive understanding of teachers' resistance to educational changes. (Peck, 2017) observed Urban School Reform in the US highlighting the challenges faced in implementing transformation initiatives, such as conflicts arising from foreign policies and local opposition. Despite these challenges, trust in urban school reform has remained strong due to outstanding city schools and programs that have helped children excel academically. (Maruthavanan, 2020) in his study of secondary school teachers in Madurai district revealed significant differences in their knowledge of the National Education Policy 2020 based on gender, years of service, family type, location, and school management type. The study also found a significant difference in NEP 2020 awareness based on years of service and family type. Limited awareness was found in (Devi & Cheluvvaraju, 2020)'s survey on stakeholders' perceptions of the 2020 National Education Policy's impact on Bengaluru's trade and management sector. Stakeholders are advised to assess the operational parameters of NEP 2020 in order to ascertain its functionality. (Khan & Bhatnagar, 2019) examined the impact of education reform in Patna on higher education. The survey revealed significant differences in students' perceptions of teaching practices and learning environments based on gender, family income, school type, and school board, but no significant differences were found based on family type. (Muskan S. 2020) focused on all the segments of the education sector and their effects on the economy. The study majorly represented the national education policy from the time of announcement by the prime minister until the varied challenges to be faced by the tutorial establishments in adopting the changes in their work surroundings supported by the National Education Policy 2020. (Kumar, A. 2021) predicts that NEP 2020 will revolutionize higher education in India, enhancing leadership quality and addressing future challenges. If implemented effectively, it could make India a global hub in education by 2030.

Research Gap

Many research papers and articles emphasise on new education policy by exploring the mechanism or the road map it provided to complete its targets and objectives. However, very few researchers have attempted to explore the perception of students and stakeholders of Gujarat state towards NEP. However, there are some research papers exploring NEP with the perspective of quality-of-life employment opportunities and technology driven education systems. Hence, the researchers have tried to gauge the awareness and perception of two main stakeholders of NEP 2020 i.e., Teachers and Students.

Research Methodology

Research Objectives

- To know whether awareness level and perception of NEP 2020 differs due to gender, level of education, year of study and age group among students in Gujarat.
- To know whether awareness level and perception of NEP 2020 differs due to gender, stream and area of teaching, educational qualification and experience among teachers in Gujarat.

Hypotheses

H₀₁ : The awareness of NEP 2020 and Perception of NEP 2020 do not differ due to demographic variables such as gender, level of education, year of study and age group among students.

H₀₂ : The awareness of NEP 2020 and Perception of NEP 2020 do not differ due to demographic variables such as gender, stream of teaching, area of teaching, educational qualification and experience among teachers (educators).

Methodology

This study has been conducted using a structured questionnaire that comprises demographic information of respondents and 28 statements linked to 10 variables of NEP 2020 on awareness on fundamental principles, multidimensional assessment, key changes in school education, key changes in higher education and perception on changes in education policy, requirement of training in staff, practical implications, the implications of NEP 2020 in the rural area, the way of teaching and learning environment. The study is conducted using non-probability convenience sampling, with teachers from the commerce, science, and arts

faculties as well as students from the UG, PG, and other higher education degree holders in commerce and management as samples. The structured questionnaire prepared for the purpose was sent to approximately 1100 respondents. We have received 528 valid responses, therefore, a total of 324 students and 204 teachers have been considered for the final data analysis. To know the difference in the awareness level and perception among teachers and students, independent two-sample t-test and one-way ANOVA was employed. Post-hoc analysis was also carried out for the rejected hypotheses from ANOVA using SPSS.

Table-1 : Test of Reliability

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
0.897	10

For the reliability test, we used SPSS to run Cronbach's Alpha on the average of all ten variables, which yielded a co-efficient of 0.897, suggesting strong consistency with the statements in table 1.

Results and Discussion

The Indian government aimed to create a national education policy to equal global standards for students. However, the success of this policy depends on the awareness of teachers and students about NEP 2020. University educators were more aware of the principles, multidimensional assessment, and key changes in higher education, while school teachers had moderate awareness. Teachers found it difficult to understand all aspects of NEP 2020 due to its lack of regional language. Most respondents had positive perceptions, except for rural areas where some teachers were skeptical about it looking to altogether different dynamics of education.

H_{01a} : The awareness of NEP 2020 and Perception on NEP 2020 does not differ due to Gender of students.

Table-2 : Independent Samples T-Test						
Variables	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Diff.	Std. Error Difference	Results
Awareness on fundamental principles in NEP 2020	-5.731	322	0.000	-0.533	0.093	Significant difference
Awareness on multidimensional assessment	-5.641	322	0.000	-0.494	0.088	Significant difference
Awareness on key changes in school education	1.318	322	0.188	0.136	0.103	Insignificant difference

(Contd...)

Awareness on key changes in higher education	0.697	322	0.486	0.067	0.096	Insignificant difference
Perception on changes in education policy	-3.045	322	0.003	-0.285	0.094	Significant difference
Perception on the requirement of training in staff	-0.329	322	0.742	-0.034	0.104	Insignificant difference
Perception on practical implications	-2.957	322	0.003	-0.285	0.096	Significant difference
Perception on implication of NEP 2020 in the rural area	2.342	322	0.020	0.280	0.119	Significant difference
Perception on the way of teaching	-2.038	322	0.042	-0.228	0.112	Significant difference
Perception on learning environment	0.637	322	0.524	0.070	0.110	Insignificant difference

Table-2 shows the independent two-sample t-test on the awareness and perception of NEP 2020 among male and female students. The results show that male students are more aware of NEP 2020's key changes in school education and higher education, but not significantly different in their perception of training and learning environment requirements, suggesting a positive perception of policy changes, practical implications, and teaching methods.

H_{01b} : The awareness of NEP 2020 and Perception of NEP 2020 does not differ due to the level of education among students.

Table-3 : ANOVA							
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Results
Awareness on fundamental principles in NEP 2020	Between Groups	49.583	2	24.792	40.111	0.000	Significant difference
	Within Groups	198.404	321	.618			
	Total	247.988	323				
Awareness on multidimensional assessment	Between Groups	24.491	2	12.246	20.203	0.000	Significant difference
	Within Groups	194.570	321	.606			
	Total	219.062	323				
Awareness on key changes in school education	Between Groups	65.492	2	32.746	49.832	0.000	Significant difference
	Within Groups	210.940	321	.657			
	Total	276.432	323				

(Contd...)

Awareness on key changes in higher education	Between Groups	123.360	2	61.680	171.950	0.000	Significant difference
	Within Groups	115.146	321	.359			
	Total	238.506	323				
Perception on changes in education policy	Between Groups	10.012	2	5.006	7.174	0.001	Significant difference
	Within Groups	223.988	321	.698			
	Total	234.000	323				
Perception on requirement of training in staff	Between Groups	12.520	2	6.260	7.548	0.001	Significant difference
	Within Groups	266.230	321	.829			
	Total	278.750	323				
Perception on practical implications	Between Groups	61.957	2	30.979	53.356	0.000	Significant difference
	Within Groups	186.373	321	.581			
	Total	248.330	323				
Perception on implication of NEP 2020 in the rural area	Between Groups	41.411	2	20.705	19.807	0.000	Significant difference
	Within Groups	335.562	321	1.045			
	Total	376.972	323				
Perception on the way of teaching	Between Groups	5.465	2	2.733	2.712	0.068	Insignificant difference
	Within Groups	323.486	321	1.008			
	Total	328.951	323				
Perception on learning environment	Between Groups	26.804	2	13.402	15.047	0.000	Significant difference
	Within Groups	285.897	321	.891			
	Total	312.701	323				

Above Table 3 shows the one-way ANOVA on the awareness and perception of NEP 2020 among the students pursuing UG, PG and other higher degree. The results shows that the awareness and perception of NEP 2020 both significantly differs as the students with PG and higher degree are more aware and positive toward the NEP 2020 and the changes it will bring to the education compared to the students pursuing UG degree except for the way of teaching as it has p-value more than 0.05.

H_{01c} : The awareness of NEP 2020 and Perception on NEP 2020 does not differ due to years of study of students.

Table-4 : ANOVA							
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Results
Awareness on fundamental principles in NEP 2020	Between Groups	40.365	2	20.183	31.204	.000	Significant difference
	Within Groups	207.622	321	.647			
	Total	247.988	323				
Awareness on multidimensional assessment	Between Groups	35.456	2	17.728	30.994	.000	Significant difference
	Within Groups	183.606	321	.572			
	Total	219.062	323				
Awareness on key changes in school education	Between Groups	107.020	2	53.510	101.389	.000	Significant difference
	Within Groups	169.413	321	.528			
	Total	276.432	323				
Awareness on key changes in higher education	Between Groups	59.824	2	29.912	53.737	.000	Significant difference
	Within Groups	178.682	321	.557			
	Total	238.506	323				
Perception on changes in education policy	Between Groups	19.927	2	9.964	14.940	.000	Significant difference
	Within Groups	214.073	321	.667			
	Total	234.000	323				
Perception on requirement of training in staff	Between Groups	89.693	2	44.846	76.144	.000	Significant difference
	Within Groups	189.057	321	.589			
	Total	278.750	323				
Perception on practical implications	Between Groups	42.799	2	21.400	33.422	.000	Significant difference
	Within Groups	205.531	321	.640			
	Total	248.330	323				
Perception on implication of NEP 2020 in the rural area	Between Groups	56.108	2	28.054	28.066	.000	Significant difference
	Within Groups	320.864	321	1.000			
	Total	376.972	323				
Perception on the way of teaching	Between Groups	14.918	2	7.459	7.624	.001	Significant difference
	Within Groups	314.033	321	.978			
	Total	328.951	323				
Perception on learning environment	Between Groups	68.668	2	34.334	45.163	.000	Significant difference
	Within Groups	244.033	321	.760			
	Total	312.701	323				

Above Table 4 shows the one-way ANOVA on the awareness and perception of NEP 2020 among the students in their 1st, 2nd and 3rd year of their study. The results shows that the awareness and perception of NEP 2020 both significantly differs as the students with 2nd and 3rd years are more aware and positive toward the NEP 2020 and the changes it will bring to the education compared to the students.

H_{01d} : The awareness of NEP 2020 and Perception on NEP 2020 does not differ due to Age group of students.

Table-5 : ANOVA							
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Results
Awareness on fundamental principles in NEP 2020	Between Groups	43.677	2	21.838	34.311	.000	Significant difference
	Within Groups	204.311	321	.636			
	Total	247.988	323				
Awareness on multidimensional assessment	Between Groups	2.905	2	1.452	2.157	.117	Insignificant difference
	Within Groups	216.157	321	.673			
	Total	219.062	323				
Awareness on key changes in school education	Between Groups	23.372	2	11.686	14.823	.000	Significant difference
	Within Groups	253.060	321	.788			
	Total	276.432	323				
Awareness on key changes in higher education	Between Groups	61.879	2	30.940	56.229	.000	Significant difference
	Within Groups	176.627	321	.550			
	Total	238.506	323				
Perception on changes in education policy	Between Groups	.000	2	.000	.000	1.000	Insignificant difference
	Within Groups	234.000	321	.729			
	Total	234.000	323				
Perception on requirement of training in staff	Between Groups	21.777	2	10.888	13.601	.000	Significant difference
	Within Groups	256.973	321	.801			
	Total	278.750	323				
Perception on practical implications	Between Groups	9.442	2	4.721	6.344	.002	Significant difference
	Within Groups	238.888	321	.744			
	Total	248.330	323				
Perception on implication of NEP 2020 in the rural area	Between Groups	31.362	2	15.681	14.564	.000	Significant difference
	Within Groups	345.611	321	1.077			
	Total	376.972	323				
Perception on the way of teaching	Between Groups	21.567	2	10.783	11.261	.000	Significant difference
	Within Groups	307.384	321	.958			
	Total	328.951	323				
Perception on learning environment	Between Groups	15.106	2	7.553	8.147	.000	Significant difference
	Within Groups	297.594	321	.927			
	Total	312.701	323				

Above Table-5 shows the one-way ANOVA on the awareness and perception of NEP 2020 among students with various age groups. The results shows significant differences in student awareness and perception, except for multidimensional assessment, among different age groups, with students being more skeptical about policy changes' effectiveness.

H_{02a} : The awareness of NEP 2020 and Perception of NEP 2020 does not differ due to Gender among teachers (educators).

Variables	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Diff.	Std. Error Difference	Results
Awareness on fundamental principles in NEP 2020	-.633	201	.528	-.087	.137	Insignificant difference
Awareness on multidimensional assessment	1.477	201	.141	.207	.140	Insignificant difference
Awareness on key changes in school education	2.952	201	.004	.409	.138	Significant difference
Awareness on key changes in higher education	-1.347	201	.179	-.183	.136	Insignificant difference
Perception on changes in education policy	-.356	201	.722	-.029	.081	Insignificant difference
Perception on requirement of training in staff	.729	201	.467	.120	.165	Insignificant difference
Perception on practical implications	-2.170	201	.031	-.231	.106	Significant difference
Perception on implication of NEP 2020 in the rural area	-2.172	201	.031	-.264	.122	Significant difference
Perception on the way of teaching	2.424	201	.016	.303	.125	Significant difference
Perception on learning environment	-.095	201	.925	-.010	.101	Insignificant difference

Above Table-6 shows the independent two-sample t-test on the awareness and perception of NEP 2020 among the male and female teachers. The results shows that awareness of key changes in school education among male and female teachers is similar, but perceptions of practical implications, rural area implications, and teaching methods differ significantly, with p-values greater than 0.05.

H_{02b} : The awareness of NEP 2020 and Perception of NEP 2020 does not differ due to the stream of teaching among teachers (educators).

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Results
Awareness on fundamental principles in NEP 2020	Between Groups	7.616	2	3.808	4.193	.016	Significant difference
	Within Groups	181.625	200	.908			
	Total	189.241	202				

(Contd...)

Awareness on multidimensional assessment	Between Groups	16.862	2	8.431	9.214	.000	Significant difference
	Within Groups	183.000	200	.915			
	Total	199.862	202				
Awareness on key changes in school education	Between Groups	28.668	2	14.334	16.559	.000	Significant difference
	Within Groups	173.125	200	.866			
	Total	201.793	202				
Awareness on key changes in higher education	Between Groups	24.185	2	12.093	14.826	.000	Significant difference
	Within Groups	163.125	200	.816			
	Total	187.310	202				
Perception on changes in education policy	Between Groups	3.638	2	1.819	5.821	.003	Significant difference
	Within Groups	62.500	200	.313			
	Total	66.138	202				
Perception on requirement of training in staff	Between Groups	1.047	2	.524	.382	.683	Insignificant difference
	Within Groups	274.125	200	1.371			
	Total	275.172	202				
Perception on practical implications	Between Groups	12.328	2	6.164	11.797	.000	Significant difference
	Within Groups	104.500	200	.523			
	Total	116.828	202				
Perception on implication of NEP 2020 in the rural area	Between Groups	.909	2	.455	.598	.551	Insignificant difference
	Within Groups	152.125	200	.761			
	Total	153.034	202				
Perception on the way of teaching	Between Groups	8.082	2	4.041	5.244	.006	Significant difference
	Within Groups	154.125	200	.771			
	Total	162.207	202				
Perception on learning environment	Between Groups	11.293	2	5.647	12.209	.000	Significant difference
	Within Groups	92.500	200	.463			
	Total	103.793	202				

Above Table-7 shows the one-way ANOVA on the awareness and perception of NEP 2020 among teachers with different stream of teaching. The results shows significant differences in teachers' awareness and perceptions, except for the perception of staff training requirements and the effectiveness of NEP 2020 in rural areas.

H_{02c} : The awareness of NEP 2020 and Perception of NEP 2020 does not differ due to the area of teaching among teachers (educators).

Table-8 : ANOVA							
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Results
Awareness on fundamental principles in NEP 2020	Between Groups	15.641	1	15.641	18.110	.000	Significant difference
	Within Groups	173.600	201	.864			
	Total	189.241	202				
Awareness on multidimensional assessment	Between Groups	1.373	1	1.373	1.391	.240	Insignificant difference
	Within Groups	198.489	201	.988			
	Total	199.862	202				
Awareness on key changes in school education	Between Groups	.193	1	.193	.193	.661	Insignificant difference
	Within Groups	201.600	201	1.003			
	Total	201.793	202				
Awareness on key changes in higher education	Between Groups	9.238	1	9.238	10.428	.001	Significant difference
	Within Groups	178.072	201	.886			
	Total	187.310	202				
Perception on changes in education policy	Between Groups	5.666	1	5.666	18.832	.000	Significant difference
	Within Groups	60.472	201	.301			
	Total	66.138	202				
Perception on requirement of training in staff	Between Groups	1.550	1	1.550	1.139	.287	Insignificant difference
	Within Groups	273.622	201	1.361			
	Total	275.172	202				

(Contd...)

Perception on practical implications	Between Groups	4.205	1	4.205	7.505	.007	Significant difference
	Within Groups	112.622	201	.560			
	Total	116.828	202				
Perception on implication of NEP 2020 in the rural area	Between Groups	.434	1	.434	.572	.450	Insignificant difference
	Within Groups	152.600	201	.759			
	Total	153.034	202				
Perception on the way of teaching	Between Groups	1.051	1	1.051	1.311	.254	Insignificant difference
	Within Groups	161.156	201	.802			
	Total	162.207	202				
Perception on learning environment	Between Groups	.388	1	.388	.753	.386	Insignificant difference
	Within Groups	103.406	201	.514			
	Total	103.793	202				

Above Table-8 shows the one-way ANOVA on the awareness and perception of NEP 2020 among teachers with different area of teaching (school teachers, professors and departmental faculties). The results shows that teachers' awareness of fundamental principles and key changes in schools and higher education varies, while their perception of educational policy changes and they are skeptical about implication and implementation of NEP 2020.

H_{02d} : The awareness of NEP 2020 and Perception of NEP 2020 does not differ due to educational qualification among teachers (educators).

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Results
Awareness on fundamental principles in NEP 2020	Between Groups	15.116	5	3.023	3.420	.005	Significant difference
	Within Groups	174.125	197	.884			
	Total	189.241	202				
Awareness on multidimensional assessment	Between Groups	42.945	5	8.589	10.783	.000	Significant difference
	Within Groups	156.917	197	.797			
	Total	199.862	202				

(Contd...)

Awareness on key changes in school education	Between Groups	73.751	5	14.750	22.694	.000	Significant difference
	Within Groups	128.042	197	.650			
	Total	201.793	202				
Awareness on key changes in higher education	Between Groups	9.977	5	1.995	2.217	.054	Significant difference
	Within Groups	177.333	197	.900			
	Total	187.310	202				
Perception on changes in education policy	Between Groups	8.680	5	1.736	5.952	.000	Significant difference
	Within Groups	57.458	197	.292			
	Total	66.138	202				
Perception on requirement of training in staff	Between Groups	69.547	5	13.909	13.326	.000	Significant difference
	Within Groups	205.625	197	1.044			
	Total	275.172	202				
Perception on practical implications	Between Groups	10.078	5	2.016	3.720	.003	Significant difference
	Within Groups	106.750	197	.542			
	Total	116.828	202				
Perception on implication of NEP 2020 in the rural area	Between Groups	7.784	5	1.557	2.112	.066	Insignificant difference
	Within Groups	145.250	197	.737			
	Total	153.034	202				
Perception on the way of teaching	Between Groups	7.040	5	1.408	1.788	.117	Insignificant difference
	Within Groups	155.167	197	.788			
	Total	162.207	202				
Perception on learning environment	Between Groups	7.251	5	1.450	2.959	.013	Significant difference
	Within Groups	96.542	197	.490			
	Total	103.793	202				

Above Table-9 shows the one-way ANOVA on the awareness and perception of NEP 2020 among teachers with different educational qualifications. The results shows that teachers' awareness and perception vary significantly based on their educational qualifications, with differences in perception only observed in rural areas and teaching methods/pedagogy.

H_{02e} : The awareness of NEP 2020 and Perception of NEP 2020 does not differ due to experience among teachers (educators).

Table-10 : ANOVA							
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Results
Awareness on fundamental principles in NEP 2020	Between Groups	13.241	2	6.621	7.524	.001	Significant difference
	Within Groups	176.000	200	.880			
	Total	189.241	202				
Awareness on multidimensional assessment	Between Groups	.129	2	.064	.064	.938	Insignificant difference
	Within Groups	199.733	200	.999			
	Total	199.862	202				
Awareness on key changes in school education	Between Groups	.060	2	.030	.030	.971	Insignificant difference
	Within Groups	201.733	200	1.009			
	Total	201.793	202				
Awareness on key changes in higher education	Between Groups	3.310	2	1.655	1.799	.168	Insignificant difference
	Within Groups	184.000	200	.920			
	Total	187.310	202				
Perception on changes in education policy	Between Groups	6.805	2	3.402	11.468	.000	Significant difference
	Within Groups	59.333	200	.297			
	Total	66.138	202				
Perception on requirement of training in staff	Between Groups	22.106	2	11.053	8.735	.000	Significant difference
	Within Groups	253.067	200	1.265			
	Total	275.172	202				
Perception on practical implications	Between Groups	4.561	2	2.280	4.063	.019	Significant difference
	Within Groups	112.267	200	.561			
	Total	116.828	202				
Perception on implication of NEP 2020 in the rural area	Between Groups	13.701	2	6.851	9.833	.000	Significant difference
	Within Groups	139.333	200	.697			
	Total	153.034	202				

(Contd...)

Perception on the way of teaching	Between Groups	29.140	2	14.570	21.899	.000	Significant difference
	Within Groups	133.067	200	.665			
	Total	162.207	202				
Perception on learning environment	Between Groups	13.126	2	6.563	14.478	.000	Significant difference
	Within Groups	90.667	200	.453			
	Total	103.793	202				

Above Table-10 shows the one-way ANOVA on the awareness and perception of NEP 2020 among teachers with difference experience level. The results shows that there are no significant difference in teachers' awareness of the fundamental principles of NEP 2020, but significant differences in their perceptions of the policy.

Post-Hoc Analysis

The hypotheses H01a to H01d, H02b, H02d and H02e were all rejected, as indicated in table 11. Thus, post-hoc tests were performed for the hypotheses H01b, H01c, H01d, H02b, H02d, and H02e because the ANOVA results indicated p-values less than 0.05 for these hypotheses. A detailed post-hoc analysis was performed to determine which factors had a significant difference. The results of the summarised Post-hoc Analysis are given below.

Table-11 : Summarised Post-Hoc Results		
Hypothesis	Hypothesis Results	Post-Hoc Difference
H01b: The awareness of NEP 2020 and Perception on NEP 2020 does not differ due to level of education in students.	Rejected	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Students pursuing PG and Higher degrees are more aware of fundamental principles, multidimensional assessment, key changes in school education and key changes in higher education in NEP 2020. Students with higher degrees are more positive toward changes in education policy and ways of teaching Students with higher degrees are more positive toward changes in education policy and ways of teaching
H01c: The awareness of NEP 2020 and Perception on NEP 2020 does not differ due to years of study in students.	Rejected	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Students studying in their 1st and 3rd year are more aware about the fundamental principles in NEP 2020, multidimensional assessment, key changes in school education and key changes in higher education and more positive toward learning environment. Student in their 1st year of study are more positive toward changes in education policy while 1st and 3rd year students are more positive toward requirement of training in staff, practical implications, and implication of NEP 2020 in the rural area.

(Contd...)

H01d: The awareness of NEP 2020 and Perception on NEP 2020 does not differ due to age group in students.	Rejected	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students with the age group of 18 to 21 years are positive toward requirement of training in staff and way of teaching while the student with age group of 22 to 25 years are more aware of fundamental principles in NEP 2020, key changes in school education and higher education and have positive perception on requirement of training in staff, implication of NEP 2020 in rural area and learning environment. • The students above the 25 age are more aware about fundamental principles in NEP 2020, key changes in school education and have positive perception of practical implication of NEP 2020.
H02b: The awareness of NEP 2020 and Perception of NEP 2020 does not differ due to the stream of teaching among teachers (educators).	Rejected	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The educators with arts streams are more aware about the fundamental principles of NEP 2020, key changes in school education and higher education and have more positive perception on changes in education policy and way of teaching. • The educators with commerce stream are more aware about the multidimensional assessment while they have positive perception toward way of teaching and learning environment.
H02d: The awareness of NEP 2020 and Perception of NEP 2020 does not differ due to educational qualification among teachers (educators).	Rejected	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • From post-hoc analysis, it was observed that educators having masters' degree and above were more aware about the fundamental principles in NEP 2020., multidimensional assessments, key changes in school and higher education • Also the educators having masters' degree and above were more positive toward overall perception on NEP 2020.
H02e: The awareness of NEP 2020 and Perception of NEP 2020 does not differ due to experience among teachers (educators).	Rejected	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • From post-hoc analysis, it was observed that educators having 10 years' experience and more were more aware about the fundamental principles in NEP 2020., multidimensional assessments, key changes in school and higher education • Also the educators having 10 years' experience and more were more positive toward overall perception on NEP 2020.

Major Findings

- The awareness of fundamental principles, multidimensional assessment, and Perception of changes in educational policy, practical implication, the implications in rural areas and the way of teaching differed as male students were more aware and had a positive perception of NEP 2020 in Gujarat.

- The level of education and years of study significantly differs in the awareness and perception of NEP 2020 as the higher degree holder students and student in their final years were more aware and positive for NEP 2020.
- Awareness and perception of NEP 2020 also significantly differ due to the students' age group as the students above 21 years were more aware of the fundamental principles, key changes in school and higher education and had positive perception of requirements in training in staff, implication in rural area, way of teaching and learning environment.
- Awareness and perception of NEP 2020 do not significantly differ due to the Gender of educators as only awareness of key changes in school education and perception of practical implications, implication of NEP 2020 in rural areas and way of teaching had p-value less than 0.05.
- Awareness and perception of NEP 2020 do significantly differ due to the stream of educators as the educators belonging to the commerce and management stream were more aware and had positive perception of NEP 2020 compared to Science and Arts stream.
- Awareness and perception of NEP 2020 do not significantly differ due to the area of teaching (Schools and Colleges) of educators as ANOVA showed insignificant differences in the majority of variables.
- Awareness and perception of NEP 2020 do not significantly differ due to the Gender of educators as only awareness of key changes in school education and perception of practical implications, implication of NEP 2020 in rural areas and way of teaching had p-value less than 0.05.
- Awareness and perception of NEP 2020 do significantly differ due to the stream of educators as the educators belonging to the commerce and management stream were more aware and had positive perception of NEP 2020 compared to Science and Arts stream.
- Awareness and perception of NEP 2020 do not significantly differ due to the area of teaching (Schools and Colleges) of educators as ANOVA showed insignificant differences in the majority of variables.

Major Suggestions

- There is still a need for more sensitization programs on NEP 2020, as many students are still unaware of several benefits NEP 2020 would bring to their development.

- Similarly for educators, they are required to go through various development programs which can lead to a better understanding of what NEP 2020 changes and how they can absorb it in their teaching.

Limitations of the Study

1. The study is confined to only Gujarat state.
2. The study observes the awareness level and perception of respondents only.
3. The awareness level and perception of other stakeholders are not studied.

Future Scope of the Study

1. Researchers can study the awareness and perception of NEP 2020 in others states of India.
2. Researchers can also study other aspects or salient features of NEP.
3. The other stakeholders such as parents, employers etc. can also be studied for their opinion on various features and effective implementation of NEP 2020.

Usefulness of the Study

The study is helpful to understand the point of view of the students and teachers who are directly related to the changes in New Education Policy 2020. This will enable the policy makers to know the thoughts and point of view they have upon understanding how the NEP will bring changes to the education system in true sense and measures required to be taken for producing employment ready youth focusing on skill building instead of rote learning. This study will become a guiding path for it.

Conclusion

Previous studies in India show moderate awareness among stakeholders about the National Education Policy 2020, which is alarming as successful implementation relies on positive awareness and understanding of the policy. (Saraswathy & Nagavalli) (Maruthavanan, 2020) The present study observed that the educators were more aware of the various aspects of NEP 2020 and had more positive perceptions toward implementing NEP 2020. Similarly, the students also have moderate awareness about NEP 2020 but their perception is also somewhat positive as they expect the NEP 2020 will help them become industry-ready. However, simply having a positive perception will not ensure successful implementation. Rather, continual evaluation and monitoring are required to achieve the desirable outcomes of NEP 2020.

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